

Teachers' pedagogical Practices in Relation to Students' Engagement in Blended Learning

¹Mhie B. Daniel, MAEd

²Haydee D. Villanueva, PhD
Misamis University

Abstract:- Teachers' ways of handling classes and students' interest and effort in their studies are essential in the new normal education. This study was conducted in one of the private institutions in Ozamiz City, Philippines, and explored the teachers' pedagogical practices in relation to the student's engagement in blended learning. The descriptive-correlational research design was used in the study. A total of 120 students served as the respondents who were chosen through purposive and quota sampling techniques. The researcher-made Teachers' Pedagogical practices and Students' Engagement in Blended Learning Questionnaires were used in gathering the data. Mean, standard deviation and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient were used in analyzing the data gathered. The results revealed the very great extent of the teachers' pedagogical practices and the very high students' engagement in the blended learning modality. Furthermore, the teachers' pedagogical practices were highly related to the student's engagement in modality. The study concludes that the teachers have exerted their best efforts in the modality used for delivering education. It is recommended that teachers sustain their pedagogical practices in blended learning to ensure the holistic engagement of their students in the teaching-learning process.

Keywords: *Blended Learning, Engagement, Pedagogical Practices, Philippines, Students, Teacher.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The pandemic has caused havoc and disruption, affecting the educational system worldwide, including higher education institutions (HEIs). Nevertheless, the health crisis has propelled HEIs to avail of new and innovative methods of delivering education to learners (Dennis, 2021). To maintain competitiveness in the educational system, academic institutions have to offer learning programs that can be delivered digitally or through online modality (Kamssu&Kouam, 2018). While instruction shifted to a virtual platform (Morgan, 2020), e-learning has become increasingly valuable in higher education institutions to improve educational experiences through changes in traditional classroom teaching and learning techniques (Kim et al., 2019).

A whole new world of participation in the classroom is made possible by e-learning, blended learning, and mobile learning (Bartolome et al., 2018). In this vein, technology

plays an essential role in today's education like in blended learning as a means of teaching-learning process (Pisoni, 2019).

Occasionally referred to as hybrid learning, blended learning (BL) is a type of instruction that combines in-person instruction and virtual delivery of learning process. Online resources are made available even after class sessions, thus providing a more personalized environment for learning (Black &Wiliam, 2018). Thus, the modalityoffers learning experiences that are focused onthe learners (Siraj &Maskari, 2019). It allows students to be active learners where they can collaborate and communicate effectively; hone their skills in delivering information, as well as demonstrate creativity while availing of virtual resources (Ibrahim & Nat, 2019).

Pedagogical practices include approaches, methods, strategies, techniques, or tools that are useful in teaching effectively (Tang &Pua, 2021). These practices are a means for the teaching-learning process for the delivery of lessons (Chia & Lim, 2020). Pedagogical practices cater to students' academic knowledge or on how students can change themselves; pedagogical knowledge or how students can convey what they know, and disciplinary knowledge or what students know. These practices facilitate for the teachers and learners to achieve growth (Perez et al., 2020).

Engagement and attention to instruction are essential for students to learn (Gage & Gage, 2017). However, being constantly engaged can be a struggle for students in the various levels of education (Zhao et al., 2021). Therefore, it is vital to identify the factors influencing student engagement (IKahihifo, 2019). A study revealed that blended learning activities in higher education institutions focus on procedures that encourage students' cognitive, emotional, and behavioral engagements (Adams et al., 2020).

Many educational researches focused on blended learning. However, only few studies were made pertaining to teachers' pedagogical practices and students' academic engagement in blended learning. Thus, this study was conducted to address this gap in research.

In one of the private higher education institutions in Ozamiz City, Philippines, limited face-to-face classes were in place for selected programs at the tertiary level. The teachers delivered instruction for face-to-face and online classes. It was noticed that the students could understand the

concepts well if the topics discussed online by the teachers were tackled during their face-to-face classes, wherein the students demonstrated engagement in various forms. Thus, the researcher examined how teachers' pedagogical practices in blended learning could affect students' engagement. The study could shed light on the effectiveness of blended learning modality at the tertiary level of education.

II. METHODS

The descriptive-correlational design was used in the study. The design that was deemed appropriate in exploring how the pedagogical practices of teachers could be related to students' engagement in blended learning. The respondents were 120 students from the selected colleges in the private institution where the study was conducted. Purposive and quota sampling techniques were used in identifying the respondents. The following were inclusion criteria: 1) participated in face-to-face and online classes; 2) enrolled in the colleges included in the study; and 3) gave consent to participate in the study.

III. FINDINGS

➤ Teachers' Pedagogical Practices in Blended Learning

Table 1 shows that the teacher's pedagogical practices were to a very great extent (M=3.53; SD=0.40). The finding

Table 1 Teachers' Pedagogical Practices in Blended Learning (n=120)

Constructs	Mean	SD	Remarks
Teaching Techniques	3.53	0.41	Very Great Extent
Assessment Procedures	3.50	0.41	Very Great Extent
Classroom Management	3.57	0.37	Very Great Extent
Overall	3.53	0.40	Very Great Extent

Note: Pedagogical Practices Scale: 3.26-4.00 (Very Great Extent); 2.51-3.25 (Great Extent); 1.76-2.50 (Less Extent); 1.00-1.75 (Least Extent)

➤ Students' Engagement in Blended Learning

Table 2 shows that the students had a very high engagement in blended learning (M=4.46; SD=0.45). The students actively participated in both online and face-to-face discussions where they had to be engaged in their classes during instruction toward the accomplishment of activities given by their teachers. Moreover, the students' emotional engagement got the highest mean rating (M=4.51; SD=0.42). The students eagerly listened to the lessons or topics in online and face-to-face classes to indicate their emotional engagement.

The Table also shows that the students had a very high cognitive engagement (M=4.41; SD=.48). They eagerly participated in online discussions and appreciated

was true for all the constructs. The findings imply that the teachers did well in their teaching, which combined the online and face-to-face classes.

Based on the findings, the teachers' pedagogical practices in terms of teaching techniques (M=.53; SD=0.41) were to a great extent. In the modality, the teacher presented the lesson in both online and face-to-face sessions. How the teachers employed various learning strategies could be useful to the students in their learning process, especially with technology in the classroom.

On the other hand, assessment procedures utilized during online and face-to-face sessions were also demonstrated to a very great extent by teachers (M=3.50; SD=0.41). The result disclosed that teachers administered proper assessment procedures to encourage students to perform well during online and face-to-face classes. As a result, the students accomplished the assessment activities given to them in either learning modality.

It was also revealed that the teachers had much control over the classroom (M=3.57; SD=0.37). Classroom management was critical in a blended learning environment to ensure effective instruction. When teachers handled the classes well, quality learning was likely to occur.

completing all learning activities requiring their cognitive skills. Cognitive engagement required the students to invest time and effort in learning by employing deep-level thinking, metacognitive skills, and purposeful learning strategies.

Further, the students' behavioral engagement in blended learning was very high (WM=4.46; SD= 0.44). The findings revealed that during online and face-to-face classes, the students performed various online tasks prescribed by teachers, such as exploring various online resources, working well with classmates on online and face-to-face activities, participating in class discussions, and interacting with classmates for the accomplishment of activities.

Table 2 Students' Engagement in Blended Learning (n=120)

Constructs	Mean	SD	Remarks
Cognitive	4.41	0.48	Very High
Behavioral	4.46	0.44	Very High
Emotional	4.51	0.42	Very High
Overall	4.46	0.45	Very High

Note: Engagement Scale: 4.21-5.00 (Very High); 3.41-4.20 (High); 2.61-3.40 (Average); 1.81-2.60 (Low); 1.00-1.80 (Very Low)

➤ *Relationship between Extent of the Teachers' Pedagogical Practices and the Level of the Students' Engagement in Blended Learning*

Table 3 presents the relationship between the extent of the teachers' pedagogical practices and students' engagement in blended learning. It is shown that teaching technique, assessment procedures, and classroom management were highly related to how the students could be engaged cognitively, behaviorally, and emotionally.

The finding disclosed that the teachers' teaching techniques strongly influenced the students' engagement. It implies that the techniques implemented by the teacher during online and face-to-face classes greatly impacted how engaged the students were in the learning modality. The finding was similar for the teachers' assessment procedures and classroom management. The teachers could make the students the tasks and activities based on how they taught and managed the class. In this vein, the teachers could use effective strategies that foster students' active engagement in teaching-learning.

Table 3 Relationship between Extent of the Teachers' Pedagogical Practices and the Level of Students' Engagement in Blended Learning

Constructs	R value	Relationship Strength	p value	Remarks
Teaching Techniques and:				
Cognitive Engagement	0.495**	Average	<0.01	Highly Significant
Behavioral Engagement	0.521**	Average	<0.01	Highly Significant
Emotional Engagement	0.468**	Average	<0.01	Highly Significant
Assessment Procedures and:				
Cognitive Engagement	0.426**	Average	<0.01	Highly Significant
Behavioral Engagement	0.503**	Average	<0.01	Highly Significant
Emotional Engagement	0.425**	Average	<0.01	Highly Significant
Classroom Management and:				
Cognitive Engagement	0.512**	Average	<0.01	Highly Significant
Behavioral Engagement	0.544**	Average	<0.01	Highly Significant
Emotional Engagement	0.472**	Average	<0.01	Highly Significant

Note: Relationship Strength Scale: 1.00 (Perfect); 0.80-0.99 (Very Strong); 0.60-0.79 (Strong); 0.40-0.59 (Average); 0.20-0.39 (Weak); 0.01-0.19 (Very Weak); 0.00 (No Relationship), Probability Value Scale: ** $p < 0.01$ (Highly Significant); * $p < 0.05$ (Significant); $p > 0.05$ (Not significant)

IV. DISCUSSION

The teachers' pedagogical practices regarding teaching strategies, assessment procedures, and classroom management were to a great extent. In the blended learning environment, the teachers employed instructional strategies appropriate for delivering instruction to students in both online and traditional or face-to-face classroom settings. The teachers ensured they could deliver education by observing classroom practices that ensured clear instruction and assessment activities. In the blended setting where online and face-to-face instructions were combined, the students needed to stay focused, whether in face-to-face or virtual classes. Teachers use various teaching techniques and technology in delivering instruction for the students to become active learners in the class, especially with the combination of two learning modalities.

Assessment procedures include various types of assessments provided by teachers either online or in-person, before and after class. It involves instructors giving direct instructions that students can follow well and evaluate their in-depth understanding of the subject matter. The findings also showed that teachers allowed students to spend ample time to finish assignments and gave prompt comments on the latter's work, indicating the specific areas that needed to be improved. Teachers also need to create a classroom

atmosphere conducive to learning, where the students are motivated to do the tasks expected of them to perform and accomplish. In this vein, the various pedagogical practices of teachers can point to the level of engagement that the students may demonstrate in blended learning classes.

Furthermore, the students were motivated to learn new things through face-to-face classes and an online platform because of the engaging teaching methods that could positively affect their self-efficacy and engagement. During online classes, the students developed an interest in active participation, where they could apply their learnings and skills. Aside from interaction with their teachers, the students could connect well with fellow learners by accessing online resources to supplement classroom learning and accomplishing online tasks and assessment activities. They were very engaged in the learning process as facilitated by their teachers, who utilized effective pedagogical practices.

V. CONCLUSION

The teachers had given their best for the delivery of quality education to students in the tertiary level by adopting the blended learning modality. The students' mental, physical, and emotional responses were substantial in

meeting the expectations of the modality for learning, with teachers' pedagogical practices having a great influence on how well students were engaged holistically. Thus, it is recommended that teachers sustain their teaching

techniques, assessment procedures, and classroom management so that students can exhibit a desirable level of engagement in the process of learning.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Bartolomé-Pina, A., García-Ruiz, R., &Aguaded, I. (2018). Blended learning: Panorama y perspectivas. *RevistaIberoamericana De Educación a Distancia*, 21(1), 33-56. doi: Retrieved on March 22, 2022 from <http://dx.doi.org/10.5944/ried.21.1.18842>
- [2]. Black, P., &Wiliam, D. (2018). Classroom assessment and pedagogy. *Assessment in education: Principles, policy & practice*, 25(6), 551-575. Retrieved on July 06, 2022 from <https://bit.ly/300W9yV>
- [3]. Dennis, M. J. (2021). Impact and opportunities: COVID-19's effect on higher education. *College and University*, 96(2), 31-36,38. Retrieved on March 22, 2022 from <https://bit.ly/3wHtmu9>
- [4]. Gage, N. A., &MacSuga-Gage, A. S. (2017). Salient Classroom Management Skills: Finding the Most Effective Skills to Increase Student Engagement and Decrease Disruptions. *Report on emotional & behavioral disorders in youth*, 17(1), 13–18. Retrieved on June 21, 2022 from <https://bit.ly/3Ob61H8>
- [5]. IkaHihifo, T. B. K. (2019). *Self-determination theory and student emotional engagement in higher education* (Order No. 28103779). Available from ProQuest Central. (2432370419). Retrieved on March 22, 2022 from <https://bit.ly/3Os1gZw>
- [6]. Kamssu, A. J., &Kouam, R. B. (2021). The effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on university student enrollment decisions and higher education resource allocation. *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice*, 21(12), 143-153. Retrieved on March 27, 2022 from <https://bit.ly/3n6cKWI>
- [7]. Kim, H. J., Hong, A. J., & Song, H. D. (2019). The roles of academic engagement and digital readiness in students' achievements in university e-learning environments. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 1-18. Retrieved on June 21, 2022 from <https://bit.ly/3tQaw1s>
- [8]. Morgan, H. (2020). Best practices for implementing remote learning during a pandemic. *The clearing house: A journal of educational strategies, issues and ideas*, 93(3), 135-141. Retrieved on June 23, 2022 from <https://bit.ly/3uCNvyB>
- [9]. Pisoni, G. (2019). Strategies for pan-european implementation of blended learning for innovation and entrepreneurship (I&E) education. *Education Sciences*, 9(2) doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/educsci9020124>
- [10]. Saqipi, B., &Vogrinc, J. (2020). The development of teacher research as a form of developing teacher pedagogical practice. *CEPS Journal : Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal*, 10(3), 5-9. doi: Retrieved on March 22, 2022 from <http://dx.doi.org/10.26529/cepsj.1003>
- [11]. Siraj, K. K., &Maskari, A. A. (2019). Student engagement in blended learning instructional design: An analytical study. *Learning and Teaching in Higher Education: Gulf Perspectives*, 15(2), 61-79. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.18538/lthe.v15.n2.283>
- [12]. Tang, W. T., &Pua, C. Y. (2021). Embracing inclusivity through pedagogical practices: Case studies from singapore science lessons. *Asia-Pacific Science Education*, 7(2), 235-279. doi: Retrieved on June 24, 2022 from <https://doi.org/10.1163/23641177-bja10027>
- [13]. Yilmaz, E., Sahin, M., & Turgut, M. (2017). Variables Affecting Student Motivation Based on Academic Publications. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(12), 112-120. Retrieved on June 21, 2022 from <https://bit.ly/3y6KZDL>
- [14]. Zhao, Y., Lin, S., Liu, J., Zhang, J., & Yu, Q. (2021). Learning contextual factors, student engagement, and problem-solving skills: A chinese perspective. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 49(2), 1-18. doi: Retrieved on March 22, 2022 from <http://dx.doi.org/10.2224/sbp.9796>
- [15]. Zhao, H., Liu, X., & Qi, C. (2021). “Want to Learn” and “Can Learn”: Influence of Academic Passion on College Students' Academic Engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 2370. Retrieved on April 25, 2022 from <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.697822/full>